

A PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICAL STUDY OF *PTEROCARPUS MARSUPIUM*, ROXB.

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A preliminary investigation of *Pterocarpus marsupium* shows the presence of 0.017% alkaloid and 0.9% resin and also sterol bodies.

The tree *Pterocarpus marsupium*, belonging to N. O. Leguminosae, grows abundantly in Bengal, Bihar, Central India and certain parts of Southern India. The heart wood is popularly used in India as an antidiabetic drug and the bark and gum are used in diarrhoea and dysentery. The gum, which is known as Kino gum, is included in B. P. C. Since the work of Ojha and Paramjit² on the hypoglycaemic effect of the drug in rabbits, fresh attention has been aroused to the medicinal property of this plant. As no systematic study of the wood has yet been reported in the literature, in the present investigation, efforts have been made to isolate the important active principles and to study their pharmacological actions. The present paper embodies our observations on the chemical composition of the wood.

The heart wood was obtained through the courtesy of the Forest Research Institute, Dehra Dun and Forest Department, Nagpur.

EXPERIMENTAL

The wood was properly powdered and stored in air-tight container, care being taken that no portion of bark or outerwood was mixed with the heart wood powder. The drug was subjected to the usual B. P.¹ and B. P. C.² tests. The values obtained are presented in Table I.

TABLE I
Moisture and ash content in the powder.

Values.	Percentage.	Elements present.
Moisture	4.30	...
Total ash	1.22	Calcium & magnesium.
Acid-insoluble ash	0.06	Silica
Water-soluble ash	0.34	Magnesium.

Aqueous Extracts

(a) The powdered drug (5g.) was extracted with distilled water. The extract was found to be red in colour with a p_H of 5.5. On evaporation it yielded 10.3% water-soluble extractive.

(b) The drug (100 g.) was macerated in boiled water and completely extracted by percolation.

Test for flavones.—An aliquot of the above extracts was concentrated to one-tenth of the initial volume, acidified with HCl and extracted with ether, furnishing a yellow residue, which gave positive tests for flavone glycoside.

Test for tannins.—An aliquot of the extract gave the reactions for tannins with iron preparations. The phenazone test was also positive. Tests for catechins and related bodies as well as haemolysing test for saponins were negative.

Adsorption chromatography.—A column of alumina (10 × 1.5 cm.) was prepared and the aqueous extract passed through it. Three different colour bands—brown, yellow and pink were developed. These bands could not be eluted with organic solvents like acetone, benzene and alcohol but could be done with dilute solution of ammonia and hydrochloric acid. All the three bands gave positive flavone reactions.

Alcoholic Extract

The drug (50 g.) was completely extracted with 90% alcohol. The colour of the solution was bright yellowish orange with p_H 5. On evaporation it left a residue of 11.52%. An aliquot of the extract was concentrated to one fifth. A few drops of this, when added to distilled water, gave a white turbidity, showing the presence of resinous bodies. Another aliquot was extracted with dilute HCl. Dilute solution of ammonia was added and extracted with chloroform. After evaporation, it was tested with Mayer's and Hager's reagents. Both the tests for alkaloids were positive.

Adsorption chromatography.—The column was prepared as before and the alcoholic extract was passed through it. Four bands—brown, bright yellow, light pink and yellowish orange were developed. On elution they gave the following reactions.

TABLE II

Reactions of colour zones with different reagents.

Fractions.	HCl (dil.)	NaOH (dil.)	NH ₄ OH (dil.)	FeCl ₃ soln.	H ₂ SO ₄ (conc.)	H ₂ SO ₄ (conc.) on residue.
Fraction No. I (Brown)	Yellow	Red.	Red with greenish blue fluorescence	Violet	Orange ring at the junction ^a	Orange
Fraction No. II (Yellow)	Colour fading	"	"	"	"	"
Fraction No. III (Light pink)	Colorless	"	Red (without fluorescence)	Light violet	"	"
Fraction No. IV (Yellowish orange)	Yellow	"	"	"	"	"

N. B.—(i) When concentrated H₂SO₄ was added to the dry residues of different fractions a beautiful orange colour developed, which on dilution, became faint yellow or colorless.

- (ii) The action of FeCl_3 indicated that all were phenolic compounds.
- (iii) When different fractions were boiled with conc. hydrochloric acid, the filtrate gave positive Molisch reaction. Fehling's solution was also reduced immediately. All the reactions showed that flavone glycosidal compounds were present in the extract.

The percolate collected from the column, which might contain resin, alkaloid and some glycosidal bodies, was evaporated and extracted with water. This aqueous solution was tested with (a) Molisch reagent and (b) Fehling's solution, for the presence of glycoside, but both were negative. The residue left after the above extraction contained resin and alkaloid.

Ethereal Extract -

The drug (5 g.) was extracted with ether. The extract was bright yellow in colour and gave 2.4% residue on evaporation. This solution was passed through an adsorption column as before. The yellow pigment was adsorbed and found to be identical with the second zone observed from the alcoholic extract. The percolate collected was evaporated and dissolved in 90% alcohol. The alcoholic solution gave the reaction for resin and alkaloid, and the alcohol-insoluble residue was found to be of fatty nature. The fat collected was subjected to the B. P. tests for the extraction of unsaponifiable matter. The matter obtained was dissolved in benzene and kept in the refrigerator for crystallisation. Rhomboid shaped small crystals were obtained which gave positive sterol reactions.

Chloroform Extract

The drug (5 g.) was extracted with chloroform. The colour of the solution was yellow. On evaporation, it left a solid residue of 0.24%. The solution was passed through an adsorption column for removing the colouring matter. The percolate collected was tested for glycoside as before but with negative results.

From the above analysis, it would be seen that the wood contains two important active principles, namely, alkaloid and resin.

Estimation of alkaloid was done by the following three methods :

Method I.—The powder (50 g.) was mixed with lime (5 g.) and extracted with chloroform in a Soxhlet apparatus. The solution was concentrated and extracted with dilute hydrochloric acid. This was made alkaline and extracted with chloroform. Chloroform was removed and the amount of alkaloid, after further purification, was found out to be 0.0172%.

Method II.—The drug (50 g.) was macerated with alcohol containing 5 ml. of dilute solution of ammonia and then extracted with alcohol in a Soxhlet

apparatus. The extract was concentrated and added to 50 ml. of water containing 5 ml. of dilute HCl with constant stirring. The mixture was filtered and the precipitate was washed with acidulated water. The combined aqueous solution was concentrated, basified and extracted with chloroform as in Method I. Percentage of alkaloid obtained was 0.0164.

Method III.—The drug (50 g.) was macerated with 500 ml. of Prolius fluid in a stoppered flask and kept for two days. It was then transferred to a percolator and extracted with chloroform-ether mixture. Most of the solvent was removed and extracted with dilute hydrochloric acid. The rest of the procedure was the same as in Method I. Percentage of alkaloid obtained was 0.0176.

Estimation of resin.—This was carried out by the following two methods.

Method I.—The Method of A.O.A.C. for extraction of podophyllum resin was used with a slight modification. The drug (50 g.) was extracted with 90% alcohol. It was then concentrated and the solution slowly poured into acidulated water, stirring constantly throughout the process. (If it was not stirred, lumps of resin were formed, which were difficult to purify. Similarly if water was added to the alcoholic solution, coagulated masses of resin were formed, which also were difficult to purify). The mixture was kept in the refrigerator for 24 hours and then filtered. The resin collected was washed with acidulated water and dissolved in alcohol from which it was further purified. Percentage of resin obtained was 0.80.

Method II.—The drug (20 g.) was extracted with alcohol and the alcoholic solution passed through an adsorption column of alumina. All the colouring matters were adsorbed. The liquid showed a faint yellow colour. This was concentrated below 50° and poured in acidulated water as in the above method. Percentage of resin obtained was 0.91.

Properties of the resin.—Buff colour of the resin darkened to brown on exposure to light and also above 25°. It was readily soluble in ether, alcohol, chloroform, acetone and benzene, very soluble in dilute caustic soda solution, sparingly soluble in petroleum ether, and insoluble in water and dilute HCl.

Red coloration with H_2SO_4 (conc.) turned pink on addition of distilled water. HCl (conc.) and $FeCl_3$ solution had no effect. No reduction of Fehling's solution, after boiling with dilute HCl, was noticed, indicating that the resin was not of glycosidal nature. This was soluble in dilute NaOH from which it could be reprecipitated by HCl (dil.), indicating its acidic nature.

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